

The Role of Imperative Verbs in Reading Passages of Vietnamese Textbooks for Grades 4 And 5

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ABSTRACT: Based on the theory of verbs and the content of reading passages in Grade 4 and Grade 5 Vietnamese textbooks, this article clarifies the role of the imperative verb group in forming and developing language skills: reading, writing, speaking, and listening. Research results show that imperative verbs are not merely pure grammatical units but also important tools that help students effectively receive and produce texts, contributing to the development of communicative competence for upper primary school students.

KEYWORDS: imperative verbs; skills; reading; writing; speaking; listening

I. INTRODUCTION

In the Vietnamese part-of-speech system, imperative verbs play a crucial role in expressing communicative content. Grades 4 and 5 represent an important transitional stage for students in perfecting language use skills, moving from recognition to application. The 2018 General Education Program for Vietnamese also requires students to not only master linguistic knowledge but also use language as a tool for effective and appropriate communication. In our view, imperative verbs in Grade 4 and 5 Vietnamese textbooks are not merely grammatical content but also vital tools for the comprehensive training of language skills, including reading comprehension, speaking, listening, and writing. Thereby, they contribute to the formation and development of communicative competence for primary students.

II. RESEARCH METHODS

The article utilizes theoretical analysis combined with descriptive methods to evaluate the role of imperative verbs in the reading passages of Grade 4 and 5 Vietnamese textbooks (belonging to three book sets: *Connecting Knowledge to Life*, *The Kite*, and *Creative Horizons*).

III. RESEARCH RESULTS

A. Theoretical Issues Regarding Imperative Verbs

1. Concept of Imperative Verbs

Imperative verbs are understood as a sub-type of transitive verbs, denoting an action performed by a subject to request that an object perform or refrain from performing a certain action; grammatically, they have the capacity to govern two complements.

2. Classification of Imperative Verbs

Based on their meanings, imperative verbs in Vietnamese can be classified as follows:

- Verbs indicating requests or proposals

These verbs express polite and gentle requests, often appearing in daily communication. This sub-type includes: *yêu cầu* (request), *đề nghị* (propose/suggest), *mời* (invite)...

- Verbs indicating advice or encouragement

These verbs express an influence aimed at orienting or encouraging the object to perform an action. This sub-type includes: *khuyến* (advise), *động viên* (encourage), *giục* (urge), *nhắc* (remind)...

- Verbs indicating asking for favors

These verbs express a request characterized by reliance on the object's help. This sub-type includes: *nhờ* (ask for help), *cậy* (rely on).

- Verbs indicating commanding or ordering:

These verbs express a mandatory or commanding influence, often reflecting the subject's power over the object. This sub-type includes: *bắt* (force), *buộc* (compel), *sai* (order), *ép* (pressure)...

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B. The Role of Imperative Verbs in Training Language Skills for Primary Students

1. The Role of Imperative Verbs in Contributing to the Development of Reading Comprehension Skills for Primary School Students

Reading comprehension is an important skill for primary school students. Mastering this skill not only helps develop students' language competence and foster their interest in Literature in general and Vietnamese language studies in primary school in particular, but also awakens in them a spirit of eagerness for learning as well as a love for goodness and beauty. It teaches students to think logically and to develop imaginative thinking. Understanding imperative verbs and their meanings in sentences helps students more easily comprehend the content of texts, thereby drawing meaningful lessons and relating them to themselves. Specifically:

First, imperative verbs help students identify the communicative purposes of characters in a text. Reading comprehension passages are often associated with particular characters and storylines. When students clearly recognize the purposes of imperative verbs (requesting, proposing, advising, asking for help, commanding), they are able to understand the speaker's intention and the meaning of the utterance in the text.

For example:

(1) "To help the villagers eliminate illiteracy, Teacher Bôn proposed that each village select one or two young people to attend classes and then return to teach the others."

(Chuyện một người thầy [The Story of a Teacher], Vietnamese 5, Volume 1, Cánh Diều edition)

Through the imperative verb "đề nghị" (propose/request), which does not carry a compulsory or coercive meaning, readers understand that the sentence expresses the teacher's sincere request, persuasion, and desire regarding literacy education in the village.

(2) "The King ordered a messenger to find someone to fight the invaders."

(Ông Yết Kiêu, Vietnamese 4, Volume 1, Cánh Diều edition)

The presence of the imperative verb "sai" (order/command) in the sentence shows a compulsory command from the King — the person holding supreme authority — directed toward the messenger, who occupies a lower social status.

Second, imperative verbs also contribute to clarifying the attitudes, emotions, and personality traits of characters in a text. As a result, students have a basis for analyzing characters more deeply, not only through their actions but also through their speech and manner of expression.

For example:

(3) "Uncle Hồ reminded students to remember certain people and think about certain things during the joyful moment of the first school day."

(Thư gửi các học sinh nhân ngày khai trường [Letter to Students on the Opening Day of School], Vietnamese 5, Volume 1, Kết nối tri thức với cuộc sống edition)

Through the imperative verb "nhắc" (remind), readers can perceive Uncle Hồ's gentle and heartfelt reminder to students: they should remember the contributions of those who helped them attend school. This subtle, affectionate advice also demonstrates Uncle Hồ's constant concern for the future generations of the country.

(4) "Kiều Công Tiễn trembled in fear and sent someone to plead for help from the King of Southern Han."

(Ngô Quyền đại phá quân Nam Hán [Ngô Quyền's Great Victory over the Southern Han Army], Vietnamese 4, Volume 2, Cánh Diều edition)

The imperative verb "cầu cứu" (plead for help) in the sentence expresses Kiều Công Tiễn's desperate request for assistance after committing his wrongdoing. His cowardly personality and fearful attitude as a traitor are also clearly revealed through this verb.

Third, identifying and analyzing imperative verbs also helps students better understand the communicative relationships between characters. The choice of imperative verbs reflects social status, communicative distance, and the degree of intimacy between characters. Words such as "nhờ" (ask for help) and "xin" (request/ask permission) often appear in lower-to-higher relationships (where the speaker has a lower status than the listener), while "sai" (order) and "bắt" (force) are commonly associated with higher-to-lower relationships (where the speaker holds a higher position than the listener).

For example:

(5) "I ask for your permission, Mother, to break open the piggy bank."

(Món quà [The Gift], Vietnamese 4, Volume 2, Cánh Diều edition)

This sentence is a request made by a daughter to her mother regarding breaking open the piggy bank. The imperative phrase "xin phép" (ask permission) reflects the hierarchical relationship between the speaker (the daughter) and the listener (her mother).

(6) "There was an order summoning him to the palace to treat a consort suffering from a cold."

(Cứu người trước đã [Saving People Comes First], Vietnamese 4, Volume 1, Cánh Diều edition)

This sentence refers to the royal court ordering a famous physician to enter the palace to treat a sick consort. The word "triệu" (summon) indicates a compulsory command issued by a superior to a subordinate, demonstrating the King's authority over the physician.

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Fourth, imperative verbs also help students answer reading comprehension questions more accurately and completely. In reading comprehension exercises, many questions require students to identify the meaning of an utterance, a character's attitude, or the communicative purpose. Correctly recognizing the type of imperative verb and its nuance helps students provide appropriate and clear answers.

Finally, imperative verbs contribute to improving students' expressive reading ability. Each type of imperative verb carries its own nuance (gentle, earnest, strict, etc.); therefore, understanding their meanings and usage helps students adjust their tone and intonation appropriately to match the content and emotions of the text. This not only improves reading quality but also enhances students' literary appreciation skills.

2. Role of imperative verbs in contributing to writing skills for primary students

During the teaching process at the primary school level, helping students master and correctly use imperative verbs not only contributes to consolidating grammatical knowledge but also plays a practical role in developing writing skills.

First of all, imperative verbs help students express the communicative purpose of sentences clearly. At the primary level, many students still write vague sentences that do not fully convey the writer's intention. By understanding how to use imperative verbs, students can directly express their wishes and requests. For example, to make a compulsory request or command, instead of writing "Please keep the classroom clean," students may write "I request that students do not litter in the classroom." The sentence then becomes clearer, stronger, and more persuasive.

In addition, the use of imperative verbs helps students write sentences that are appropriate to the context and communicative situation. In reality, each communicative context requires a different way of expression: sometimes advising, sometimes reminding, and sometimes requesting. For example, in a letter to a friend with the purpose of encouraging better study habits, a student may write: "I advise you to study hard in order to achieve good results!" When reminding classmates about classroom rules, students may use the sentence: "The teacher reminds students not to push when entering or leaving the classroom." When writing a paragraph calling on people to protect the environment, students may present ideas such as: "I propose that students throw rubbish in the proper place to keep the schoolyard clean and beautiful. I encourage everyone to limit the use of plastic bags and actively plant more trees. I also remind students not to break branches, pick leaves, or throw rubbish into ponds and lakes." Through the appropriate use of imperative verbs, the content of writing becomes more vivid and persuasive.

For writing tasks that require students to express opinions, such as explaining reasons for liking or disliking a character, the use of imperative verbs significantly improves the quality of students' writing. If a student only writes: "I like Dế Mèn because he is brave and admits his mistakes," the paragraph remains at the level of narration and personal feeling. However, if the student adds: "I like the character Dế Mèn because he is brave and dares to admit his mistakes when he does something wrong. Through this character, I advise students to learn from Dế Mèn's spirit of admitting mistakes and not to live selfishly so as not to regret it later," the writing reaches a higher level: it not only expresses an opinion but also draws a lesson and provides behavioral orientation. This demonstrates a development from reproductive thinking to evaluative thinking.

Finally, imperative verbs also carry educational significance in shaping attitudes and behavior. Through the frequent use of imperative expressions such as "advise," "tell," and "remind," students gradually develop the habit of speaking and writing politely, while learning to advise and respect others. This is an important factor in the holistic development of primary school students' personalities.

3. Role of imperative verbs in contributing to speaking and listening skills for primary students

Vietnamese is an essential tool in daily communication. A good command of Vietnamese helps people convey information clearly and achieve their communicative purposes effectively. If communication is considered an art, then the appropriate selection and use of imperative verbs is a crucial factor contributing to its success. These verbs not only express requests, proposals, or commands, but also reflect attitudes, levels of politeness, and the relationship between the speaker and the listener. For 4th and 5th-grade students, understanding and correctly using imperative verbs is of great significance in developing communicative competence, particularly speaking and listening skills. At this stage, students need to not only identify but also flexibly apply imperative verbs in specific communicative situations. In the 4th and 5th-grade Vietnamese curriculum, communicative situations become increasingly diverse and complex, requiring students to master the nuances of meaning as well as the appropriate usage of each imperative verb. This can be recognized through several reading texts containing imperative verbs as follows. Example (7): > "I grant you permission to take one type of weapon." — (Vietnamese 4, Volume 1, Chân trời sáng tạo edition) The core of this statement is the imperative verb "cho" (grant/allow). Unlike imperative verbs that convey harsh imposition like "cấm" (prohibit) or "bắt" (force), the verb "cho" in this context carries a mild nuance, demonstrating the King's care, trust, and appreciation for Yet Kieu's talent. The appearance of the imperative verb "cho" serves as a testament to help students realize that although they are all imperative verbs, each word carries its own expressive nuance. While some verbs create a sense of imposition and command, others express encouragement, support, and goodwill. In daily communication, choosing the right words not only helps convey the intended purpose of speech but also demonstrates behavioral culture and respect for the listener. In the story "Con sóng lan xa" (The Rippling Wave), upon seeing a flock of wild ducks swimming close to the shore, a boy, wanting to keep quiet so he could easily shoot them with his slingshot, said

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to his younger sister: Example (8): > "Now, no talking out loud, okay?" [Using the verb *cấm* - prohibit/banned] — (Vietnamese 4, Volume 2, Cánh Diều edition) The core of this statement is the imperative verb "*cấm*" (prohibit/forbid). In Vietnamese, "*cấm*" is not merely a request, but a highly coercive command, often used to establish authority and absolute prevention. The boy's use of this verb with his sister inadvertently created a dividing wall, turning a naturally close sibling relationship into a dry, rigid submission. At this moment, the verb "*cấm*" not only carries the weight of a threat but also exposes selfishness, disregarding others' feelings to achieve personal goals. The appearance of the imperative verb "*cấm*" is a valuable demonstration that helps students perceive the power of words. In daily communication, if we abuse verbs with such "commanding" and "oppressive" nuances, we will lose the connection and sincerity between human beings. Furthermore, when the verb "*cấm*" is used to serve an intention that lacks compassion—hunting small creatures—it makes the speech even heavier and less sympathetic. In the world of fairy tales, the authority of a king is often associated with ironclad commands. However, in the work "*Hoàng tử học nghề*" (The Prince Learns a Trade), faced with his son's unexpected marriage choice, the King of Persia embodies a completely different image through a reflective narrative line: "The king advised him repeatedly to no avail, so he had to send an envoy to find the girl." — (Vietnamese 5, Volume 1, Cánh Diều edition) The most humane highlight in this sentence is the imperative verb "*khuyên*" (advise/counsel). Completely different from the imposing nuance of words like "*bắt*" (force) or "*lệnh*" (command), "*khuyên*" is a verb that carries the warmth of understanding, patience, and respect. It is not only a tool to convey a father's wishes but also a testament to a tolerant heart that always places the children's free will above monarchical power. The use of the verb "*khuyên*" combined with the modifier "*mãi*" (repeatedly/persistently) portrays a persistent journey of paternal love—an effort to influence through reason and affection rather than using authority to break the prince's will. The appearance of the imperative verb "*khuyên*" in this context opens up a profound lesson on the art of human conduct for students. It affirms that true power does not lie in forcing others to follow one's will, but in the ability to persuade with sincerity. Even though the result was "to no avail", the verb "*khuyên*" created a noble moral foundation, showing that the king chose the most civilized way of dialogue to protect his child's happiness.

IV. DISCUSSION

From the research results, it can be affirmed that imperative verbs are an important “key” to the comprehensive development of language competence for Grade 4 and Grade 5 students. First, imperative verbs help students recognize the differences among expressions such as commanding, pleading for help, and advising. As a result, students not only understand the surface meaning of a text but are also able to analyze the social status, psychology, and personalities of characters. This serves as a foundation for the development of critical thinking and literary appreciation. Second, understanding the characteristics of imperative verbs helps students move beyond vague and list-like writing styles. The correct use of imperative verbs makes sentences clearer, more purposeful, and more persuasive. Third, imperative verbs also serve as a direct tool for developing communicative subtlety. Through the selection of appropriate words, students learn how to adjust their language behavior according to the listener and the communicative context. This helps them form polite, civilized, and effective communication skills.

V. CONCLUSION

Research shows that imperative verbs play a vital role in developing language competence for primary students. Therefore, teachers need to focus on exploiting these verbs during instruction. They should not stop at word-class identification but should organize activities for students to analyze, compare, and practice using them in receiving and creating texts, so that students can truly master the "art of communication" through this group of verbs.

REFERENCES

- 1) Lê A – Phan Phương Dung – Đặng Kim Dung (2014), Vietnamese Curriculum 3, Education University Publishing House.
- 2) Diệp Quang Ban – Hoàng Văn Thung (1991), Vietnamese Grammar Vol I, Education Publishing House.
- 3) Nguyễn Tài Căn (1998), Vietnamese Grammar, Hanoi National University Publishing House.
- 4) Hữu Đạt – Trần Trí Dõi – Đào Thanh Lan (1998), Foundations of Vietnamese, Education Publishing House.
- 5) Bùi Mạnh Hùng (General Editor), Vietnamese Textbooks 4, 5 - Connecting Knowledge to Life, Vol 1, 2, Vietnam Education Publishing House.
- 6) Nguyễn Văn Lộc – Nguyễn Mạnh Tiến (2017), Vietnamese Grammar, Vietnam Education Publishing House.
- 7) Nguyễn Thị Ly Kha – Trịnh Cẩm Ly (Co-editors), Vietnamese Textbooks 4, 5 – Creative Horizons, Vol 1, 2, Vietnam Education Publishing House.
- 8) Nguyễn Minh Thuyết (Editor), Vietnamese Textbooks 4, 5 – The Kite, Vol 1, 2, Ho Chi Minh City University of Education Publishing House.
- 9) Institute of Linguistics (2008), Vietnamese Grammar: Theoretical Issues, Social Sciences Publishing House.